

A Method for Characterizing Track Goodness when Design Mismatch Occurs

Sheri L. Burton, George J. Foster, John E. Gray

Combat Systems Department

Naval Surface Warfare Center, Dahlgren Division

Dahlgren, VA 22448

FAX 540-653-1996

sburton@nswc.navy.mil, gfoster@nswc.navy.mil, jgray@nswc.navy.mil

Abstract

While the Kalman filter has been theoretically shown to be optimal as a tracking filter in sensor applications, the performance of the filter can be sub-optimal when the filter parameters are poorly selected or when the filter is used to track a class of target other than that for which the filter is optimized. Constant gain, steady state versions of the Kalman filter have properties that can be easily characterized analytically and then optimized for a selected design criteria. In this paper, we use the mean squared error in velocity as the design criterion to motivate the concept of track goodness and develop two indicators of track quality. We then use one of these indicators to predict the performance of a Kalman filter and an alpha-beta filter on an accelerating target for a range of designed acceleration parameters. Finally, we compare the predicted performance of both filters against the actual performance for design parameters at, above, and below the actual target acceleration.

1. Introduction and background

Starting with the development of radar in the forties, it was noted that there is a great advantage in using state information derived from the sensor to estimate the future states of where the tracked object (target) is thought to be. This could be used to determine pointing orders for the radar, which leads to the increased likelihood that one could maintain surveillance on the target. This problem, whose initial solution dates back to Gauss [1], drove the development of increasingly sophisticated methods for target tracking which, in the late fifties, led to the formulation of the Kalman filter equations [2]. Subsequently, there has been considerable sophistication in application of the Kalman filter equations to non-sensor driven applications, such as the stock market.

The canonical problem that initially drove the development of the Kalman filter, and was viewed as a triumph of its application, was the problem of tracking satellites or ballistic missiles. It was fortunate that this problem was the first one that the Kalman filter was initially tested against. There is a well understood model of the target dynamics based on celestial mechanics. Thus, one has a good state model even provided the dynamics are not fully modeled in the filter. Furthermore, the dynamics do not change sufficiently such that one may want to change the dimension of the state vector. Therefore, if the numerical burden of a full state model can be born by ones computational facilities, the model is highly accurate and subject to only minor perturbations. A second advantage of this particular problem, from the Kalman filter's viewpoint, is that various contributions to the un-modeled behavior are known and can be modeled with a reasonably good plant noise (un-modeled behavior) structure.

The standard measurement model of signal plus noise (where noise means both randomness and unknown behavior) has a particularly fortuitous decomposition, such that the Kalman filter can take full advantage in this particular application. The "noise", or uncertainty, in the standard model can sometimes be decomposed into two distinct components, N_{mes} and N_{mod} . N_{mes} is the noise due to the measurement process and N_{mod} is the uncertainty, due to modeling error. This is exactly the decomposition that is assumed in the Kalman filter equations. It assumes that there is a good state model, and noise associated with using sensors to estimate the parameters of the state model. In addition, there is a plant noise model that is supposed to account for un-modeled behavior. The problem with this approach to target tracking is what happens when there is more than one model required to explain the un-modeled behavior that can occur. This does not occur in the ballistic environment currently, but does occur in the military sensor environment.

The military tracking environment has led to considering different methodologies than are considered

to be the normal Kalman filter design. Previously [3], we discussed using cost function criteria to select the filter coefficients rather than straight Kalman filter design criteria, as has been discussed by Kalata [4]. The mean squared error criterion provides an optimum when one's design agrees with the actual target dynamics. It would be useful to be able to characterize what the performance is when there is a design mismatch. In order to understand the effects of the mismatch, it is necessary to characterize the quality of one's design. This leads one to define a term, "track quality", we will later define as a means of characterizing design performance when a mismatch occurs. Our goal in this note is to demonstrate what happens when one designs an rms and Kalman filter to a common design criteria and each encounters targets that behave differently than the common design criteria

2. Track Goodness

The consistency [5] of a filter's estimator (statistical convergence of an estimator to its true value) does not capture the type of tracking environment we are dealing with. In military situations, there is not one target model that captures the diversity of threat dynamics that can occur. One may encounter civilian jets, subsonic cruise missiles, supersonic cruise missiles, ballistic threats, etc. simultaneously in a tracking environment. Thus, two of the three consistency properties (unbiased and non-white) fail under the normal operating conditions of the filter. One is then faced with the dilemma of characterizing how the filter is performing when it is operating correctly. Also, how does one tell when the filter is performing incorrectly? To deal with these matters, we introduce the concept of track goodness. There are several possible approaches to defining such a quality that have strengths and weaknesses.

In order to proceed, we will make the simplifying assumption that we are dealing with a single dimensional two state filter. A further simplification that we will make is that the Kalata [4] steady state solution to the Kalman filter equations is fully equivalent in performance to the non-stationary filter. Thus we have a common analytical basis on which to proceed. We will assume the Kalata relationship between α and β that

$$\beta = 2(2 - \alpha) - 4\sqrt{1 - \alpha} \quad (1)$$

for both design methodologies. The method for selection of α is to introduce the tracking index Γ which is the ratio of the measurement noise divided by the maneuverability noise.

$$\Gamma^2 = \frac{\beta^2}{1 - \alpha} = T^4 \frac{\sigma_a^2}{\sigma_m^2} \quad (2)$$

Both of these are predetermined by sensor design or by choice of the designer. One then solves the equation for α . (Note that the steady state assumption can be relaxed somewhat once the tracking index has been introduced. Variability in measurement noise can be factored in provided it does not vary too quickly, making $\Gamma = \Gamma(k)$ by the implication $\sigma_m^2 = \sigma_m^2(k)$.) The cost function method for selecting α [3] is somewhat different, though one still ends up with the equivalent of a tracking index.

$$\gamma^2 u = \frac{1 + 6u + 6u^2}{[(1+u)^2 u^2 (1+2u)^2]} \quad (3)$$

where $\alpha = \frac{1+2u}{(1+u)^2}$ and $\beta = \frac{2}{(1+u)^2}$. One then solves

(2) for $u = u(\gamma)$ to determine the filter coefficients. It was shown elsewhere [3] that this selection criteria outperformed the Kalman filter using the Kalata criteria when one was concerned with minimizing noise reduction plus bias.

The problem of design mismatch is that one has used either (2) or (3) to determine one's filter coefficients when one's design is based on a specific γ or Γ , and in fact, another γ would be more correct. It is clear that there is some degradation in performance, but to what degree? There are two possible ways to arrive at a mismatch for γ . Either the assumed measurement noise is incorrect or the target maneuverability is wrong. Because measurements of the state (position) are made directly, we will assume that the measurement noise can be determined to sufficient accuracy. The source of the design mismatch is due to maneuverability which is not a measurement state of the sensor. If we take the cost function

$$\frac{J(\alpha, \beta)}{\sigma_m^2} = K_v + L_v^2 \Gamma^2 = \frac{2\beta^2}{\alpha(4 - 2\alpha - \beta)} + \Gamma^2 \left(\frac{\alpha}{\beta} - \frac{1}{2} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

One knows (4) exactly since one is filtering with a specific α , have determined σ_m , and have γ as a design parameter. One can then take the expected value of the smoothed velocity and compute the mean squared error. One then has a measured value J_m . One can then compute the first type of track quality as

$$TQ_1 = \frac{J_m}{J_e} \quad (5)$$

Thus, the further the measured value of the cost function is from the experimental value, the worse the track quality. If the track quality is sufficiently low one should reconsider one's design assumptions.

A second definition of track quality is based on the tracking index. This method is common to either design methodology. First, note that if we assume that the α 's using either tracking index are the same, then the relationship between the two gamma's can be shown to be

$$\Gamma = 2\gamma \sqrt{\frac{2 - 3\sqrt{\beta} + \beta}{\beta - 6\sqrt{\beta} + 6}} \quad (6)$$

One can use either gamma to do the following: Assume that the experimental cost function is

$$\frac{J_e}{\sigma_m^2} = K_v + L_v^2 \gamma^2 \quad (7)$$

Assuming the α 's are those one is using for filtering, one can then use those to get the experimental γ_e^2 which is

$$\gamma_e = \frac{\left(\sqrt{\frac{J_e}{\sigma_m^2} - K_v} \right)}{L_v} \quad (8)$$

Then the second track quality is

$$TQ_2 = \frac{\gamma_m}{\gamma_e} \quad (9)$$

Using the above relationship, the Kalata gamma and resulting track quality can then be computed. In addition, there are several other cost functions besides the ones mentioned here that could also be used.

3. Simulation results

To illustrate the concept of track quality, we predict the performance of a Kalman filter and an alpha-beta filter for a specific target maneuver when different maneuver assumptions are used to design the filter. Our scenario consists of a one dimensional sensor with a measurement standard deviation $\sigma_m = 10$ m updating at a 1 Hz rate. The target remains stationary until the filters have settled into steady state. At this point the target begins a constant acceleration of 10 m/s^2 . The criterion of interest is the mean squared velocity error from (4). The Kalman filter is designed with the parameters

$$R_k = \sigma_m^2 \text{ and } Q_k = a_0^2 \begin{bmatrix} \frac{T^4}{4} & \frac{T^3}{2} \\ \frac{T^3}{2} & T^2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The filter gains for the alpha-beta filter are selected to minimize the cost function in (3) given σ_m and a_0 .

Figure 1 illustrates the predicted cost of the mismatch in design parameters for a range of design acceleration values. Manipulating these results into the form of the track quality indicator in (5) leads to Figure 2. It is interesting to note that the alpha-beta filter designed to

Figure 1

minimize the cost function is more robust against mismatch in design parameters.

Figure 2

The simulated results for 500 Monte-Carlo runs for both filters designed to $a_0 = 10 \text{ m/s}^2$ are shown in Figure 3. The dashed lines represent the predicted costs for each filter from Figure 1. The simulated results match the predictions very well. Figures 4 and 5 illustrate the simulation results for filters designed to $a_0 = 5 \text{ m/s}^2$ and $a_0 = 20 \text{ m/s}^2$ respectively. Again the results compare very well with the predicted costs from Figure 1.

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

4. Conclusions

We have discussed several different methods for comparing the results of a design mismatch between the Kalman filter technique for treating un-modeled error and the cost function design method for dealing with uncompensated error caused by threat accelerations. Our results show that the cost function method is an effective preliminary work needs to be extended to other cost functions and other methods for selecting the filter coefficients. The track quality is a means of characterizing the relative stability of the design even when mismatch occurs. Thus, it appears to be a useful alternative to consistency when design mismatch is the norm. We plan to extend this work to deal with other models of the plant noise and situations when the Kalman filter is not in steady state. The cost function method should be considered as an alternative to the Kalman filter when robustness is an issue in the tracking environment.

References

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